

THE ADVANTAGES OF TEACHING GRAMMAR USING GAMES

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Abstract: The article discusses the use of grammar games as one of the primary aspects of teaching methods in teaching foreign languages. The author defines techniques and benefits of using games in teaching grammar.

Keywords: grammar, methods, game, technique, level, studying, foreign languages.

Grammar becomes exciting and dynamic when you bring the real world into your classroom and bring your class outside. To study the structure of the simple sentence, to make the process of learning grammar understandable [3, 12-36]. The importance of grammar acquisition in language acquisition is growing, but opinions on the effectiveness of various methods for presenting vocabulary items are divided. In addition, grammar is thought to be a tedious and laborious process. Experts have observed that students enjoy using games to practice language, and that these games not only help students learn without conscious thought to the process but also help them acquire communicative competence as second language users. There are many approaches related to grammar presentation. Although educators agree that games are great learning activities for kids, many seasoned textbook and methodology authors though teachers agree that games are excellent learning activities for children, many experienced textbook and methodology manual writers have argued that games are not just time-filling activities but also help students learn without a conscious analysis or understanding of the learning process while they acquire communicative competence as second language users. Although there is much disagreement regarding the effectiveness of various approaches for presenting vocabulary items, learning grammar is often perceived as a tedious and laborious process. From the experience of some experts, they have noticed how enthusiastic students are about practicing language through games. There are several benefits to using games in foreign language instruction.

1. Games can reduce anxiety, which increases the likelihood that students will learn the language.

2. Games are very motivating and entertaining, and they can give shy students more opportunities to express their opinions and feelings.

3. Games also allow students to gain new experiences in the language that are not always possible during a typical lesson.

4. Games add variety to regular classroom activities, break the ice, and introduce new ideas.

5. Students remember information more quickly and effectively in the easy, relaxed atmosphere that using games creates.

6. Grammar games are a good way for students to practice the language because they simulate real-world situations.

7. Grammar games encourage, entertain, teach, and promote fluency. If not for any of these reasons, they should be used simply because they help students see the beauty in a foreign language and not just problems. This is the main reason to use games when studying grammar. Choosing appropriate games is also very important. There are many factors to consider when discussing games, one of which is appropriacy. If teachers want to make games profitable for the learning process, they must carefully select games that match the students' level or age or the materials that a teachers should know when to use games. Games are often used as short warm-up activities or when there is some time left at the end of the lesson. Games should not be regarded as a marginal activity filling in odd moments when the teacher and class have nothing better to do. Games ought to be at the heart of teaching foreign languages. Grammar games also lend themselves to this purpose. Games become difficult when the task or the topic is unsuitable or outside the pupils' experience.

All of the authors I consulted for my report agreed that even though grammar games only made noise and entertained students, they are still valuable to consider and use in the classroom because they inspire students, foster communicative competence, and create fluency. Some strategies to involve students in the grammar explanation stage are asking them to provide you with example sentences from their imaginations, past conversations, or the textbook; asking them to match grammatical names, example sentences, and meanings; and asking students to prepare grammar presentations for homework.

References

1. Коньшева А.В. Игровой метод в обучении иностранному языку. СПб.: КАРО, МН.: Издательство «Четыре четверти», 2008. 192 с.

2. Marianne C. Sharon H. Techniques and Resources in Teaching Grammar. Oxford Press, 1988.

3. Мухин А.М. Структура предложений и их модели. Л., 1968.

